

Eco-Friendly Cleansers Initiation for Eco-Campsite Development in Khao Yai National Park, Thailand

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Abstract : Environmental impact has occurred at Khao Yai National Park, especially the water pollution by tourist activities as a result of 800,000 tourists visiting annually. To develop an eco-campsite, eco-friendly cleansers were implemented in Lam Ta Khlong and Pha Kluay Mai Campsites for tourists and restaurants. The results indicated the positive effects of environmentally friendly cleansers on water quality in Lam Ta Khlong River and can be implemented in other protected areas to decrease chemical contamination in ecosystems.

Keywords : sustainable tourism management, eco-campsite, Khao Yai National Park, ecology

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